

Clean Code and Refactoring

Sufficient Conditions for Successful Refactoring

A RESEARCH ESSAY

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
CI	Continuous Integration
DevOps	Development and Operations Teams

ABSTRACT

Software development life cycle process describes every phase of software product development. Implementation is one of the most important phase of SDLC. With the evolution of digital era, the need of developing good quality software products in minimum time is required. DevOps is a fast growing software development paradigm where strong collaboration between development team and operations team is required. In order to fulfill the ongoing rapid changes in the tools and techniques of software engineering clean code and refactoring is the best solution. For successful refactoring, it is necessary to understand the conditions that are required for the successful refactoring. These conditions include clean code, more maintainable and readable code, selection of correct technique of refactoring, running all test cases successfully etc. The comparative analysis of these conditions depicts the impact of conditions over successfulness of refactoring and helps the software engineer to reduce the time and effort for software product development.. In this present research, the researcher uncovered all the conditions required for successful refactoring. It eventually, presented a comparative analysis for most important conditions. To validate the work statistical data collection performed to see the impact of conditions for successful refactoring. The results of research show that considering all conditions are important for successful refactoring but clean code and DevOps are the most important conditions for the successful refactoring.

Keyword- Refactoring, Software Design, Artifact, Software Quality Assurance, Code Integration, Comments, Functions, Classes, Software Testing, Code standard, DevOps

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter deals with an introduction of the conditions for successful refactoring and its impact over software development life cycle. The basic artifact of software product is its code. The implementation phase of SDLC plays an important role for testing and integration phase. With the revolution of digital age, software engineering principals and methodologies new challenges needs to be address. In order to meet the fast dead line for the new versions of software products launch and maintaining the quality assurance, refactoring is the best solution. At the end of this chapter, the problem and the methodology of finding and prioritizing the impact of conditions for successful refactoring briefly discussed.

1.1 Refactoring

Refactoring improves the design of code after it has written. It is a practice of implementing the requirements by already existing code after making necessary changes in code so it does not change the overall functionality. Refactoring aims at improving the maintainability of source code without modifying its external behavior (Traini L, *et al.*, 2021).

Refactoring is the process of changing a software system in such a way that it does not alter the external behavior of the code yet improves the internal structure. (Pressman, 2020). We can clean the code in a systematic manner using factoring so the chance of occurring errors or bugs in code will minimized.

SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT LIFE CYCLE FACTORING

FIGURE 1.1 Role of Factoring in Software Development Life Cycle

1.1.1 Rational of finding conditions for successful refactoring

For a successful refactoring, it is necessary to understand the conditions for refactoring. Refactoring can result in more complicated and bad smell code if necessary conditions for refactoring not considered. In case, where necessary conditions not considered then it can result in consuming time and effort for software development. Refactoring is mostly use to improve the reusability of code, but due to this improvement, it may increase the attack surface due to the created abstractions. Increasing the spread of security-critical classes in the design to improve modularity may result in reducing the resilience of software systems to attacks (Abid, *et al.*, 2020).

1.1.2 Motivations for the conditions of successful refactoring

Finding and applying all necessary condition of factoring results in successful refactoring can help in facing the challenges of capturing the market demand, DevOps culture, key to reduce technical cost, reduced time and effort, more reliable and easy to build incremental software development.

1.2 Software Engineering and Successful Refactoring Conditions

Refactoring is a technique that reorganize and simplifies the code (or design) of a software component without changing its functionality or behavior. Fowler defines refactoring in the following manner: “Refactoring is the process of changing a software system in such a way that it does not alter the external behavior of the code (or design) yet improves its internal structure.”

In software engineering, the following are the areas that are directly or indirectly provide some sufficient conditions for the successful refactoring such as clean code, code structure, design structure, quality assurance, programming standards, testing, and software metrics and continues integration and deployments.

1.3 Research Essay Organization

Chapter 2 surveys the existing literature about sufficient conditions for successful refactoring, gap analysis and problem statement, also describes the methodology that are for the proposed solution. Chapter 3 gives the results of the comparative analysis and summaries and concludes the whole research essay briefly. Chapter 4 gives all the bibliography in APA style.

CHAPTER 2

MAIN PART

In this chapter, we have conducted a detailed study about the sufficient conditions for the successful refactoring. In Software development life cycle, quality assurance is an umbrella activity. In implementation, a clean code provides a base for future refactoring. We studied and analyzed the previous work to find the drawbacks and weaknesses in the related work. Many research papers give the knowledge about handling refactoring just without considering any base conditions that result in bad smell code.

2.1 Review of Literature

In (Abid, *et al.*, 2020) authors presented the detailed analysis about how does refactoring impact security when improving quality and few conditions for successful condition but they not given any comparative analysis and impact of these conditions for successful refactoring.

In (AlOmar, *et al.*, 2024) presented a systematic literature review about refactoring. In this paper, authors aim at reviewing the current body of knowledge on existing Extract Method refactoring research and explore their limitations and potential improvement opportunities for future research efforts. That is, Extract Method is considered one of the most widely-used refactorings, but difficult to apply in practice as it involves low-level code changes such as statements, variables, parameters, return types, etc. Hence, researchers and practitioners begin to be aware of the state-of-the-art and identify new research opportunities in this context.

In (Haendler T. *et al.*, 2019) authors presented some a competence framework for software refactoring by applying Bloom's revised taxonomy for educational objectives. In particular, they describe the competence levels by combining knowledge and cognitive-process dimensions but they not considered the role of sufficient conditions for the successful refactoring.

Vasileva A. *et al.* (2016), proposed a long-term integration of quality aspects can be ensured by the application of measurement and didactic methods in several iteration cycles.

In (Traini L, *et al.*, 2021) authors discussed how software refactoring impacts execution time. The goal of the study is to investigate the impact of refactoring operations on software performance. Measuring performance encompasses multiple metrics, such as response time, utilization, etc.

The role of sufficient conditions is discuss but not highlighted for the successful refactoring.

2.2 Statement of Problem

Existing literature not provided or partially provided the importance of sufficient conditions for the successful refactoring. In (Abid, *et al.*, 2020) they not given any comparative analysis and impact of these conditions for successful refactoring. In (Haendler T. *et al.*, 2019) they not considered the role of sufficient conditions for the successful refactoring. Vasileva A. *et al.* (2016), they partially discussed about few conditions. In (Traini L, *et al.*, 2021) The role of sufficient conditions are discussed but not highlighted for the successful refactoring.

2.2.1 Research Objectives

To uncover all the sufficient conditions for successful refactoring and comparative analysis of conditions over the impact of DevOps and quality assurance.

2.2.2 Research Questions

Our research is about finding sufficient conditions for successful refactoring. However, the following issues must consider:

RQ1. What are the sufficient conditions for refactoring?

RQ2. How sufficient conditions for refactoring can compared to find the impact over software quality and DevOps?

2.3 Sufficient Conditions for Successful Refactoring

After detailed review of literature following sufficient conditions are necessary for the successful refactoring.

2.3.1 Clean Code and Refactoring

The term clean code is use in software engineering to describe the code quality. Clean code improves readability and maintainability. The clean code provides a strong base to refactor the code.

Refactoring refers to the process of improving the code without changing its external behavior. To have clean code it is necessary to have meaningful names for variables, classes and functions. Functions provide work according to their functionality, so each function have fewer lines of code and perform a particular task. For clean code, the indentation plays an important role and readability enhancement. Proper documentation of code also facilitates in creation of clean code. The documentation by the proper use of comments in code, error handling routines and proper error messages generates clean code. By Inheritance, polymorphism and method over riding code duplication is minimized that help to have clean code. The clean code is the base condition for the successful refactoring. Above described characteristics of clean code are necessary for successful refactoring.

2.3.2 Understand Software Design and Refactoring

Good understanding of existing code and design structure and layout is a sufficient condition for successful refactoring. By better understanding of software design and dependability, refactoring process preserves the functionality of code and improves the design structure and code quality metrics.

2.3.3 Testing and Refactoring

In order to measure the successfulness of code refactoring, a set of test cases plays an important role. These test cases run after refactoring to check the code is still providing the required functionality. Having a robust set of test cases is one of the conditions for the successful refactoring.

2.3.4 Clear Objective of Refactoring

Clear objective of code factoring is the most important condition for successful refactoring. Refactoring process improves code readability, performance or remove technical debt or bad small code. Programmers need to understand that what his ultimate goal is after refactoring. By clear refactoring objectives, programmer will be in a position to measure the successfulness of refactoring.

2.3.5 Follow Coding standards and Refactoring

For successful refactoring, it is necessary to follow the coding standards. Therefore, refactoring process will be smooth and a strong collaboration and communication between development team established that ensures the success of refactoring.

2.3.6 Incremental steps and Refactoring

Performing refractory by breaking down refactoring into smaller and maintainable parts ensure the success of refactoring. Gradual changes in code structure, keep the code maintainable that results in successful refactoring.

2.3.7 Use of DevOps and Refactoring

It is a necessary condition for the successful refactoring to use of DevOps methods and tools. Refactoring need monitoring and managing measurements that are easy with DevOps tools and culture systems. Performance and behavior of code measured before and after refactoring. Automated backup, automated version controls, rollbacks, collaboration and continuous integration process using tools like Visual Studio, Docker, Eclipse, Net beans, Small Talk ensures the successful refactoring.

2.4 Comparative analysis of sufficient conditions for successful refactoring

Comparative analysis of sufficient conditions for successful refactoring shown in Table 2.1. Direct impact means that the condition directly improve the refactored code and Indirect means that there are some pre condition along with this condition for the successful refactoring.

TABLE 2.1 Impact of Conditions on Refactoring

Sufficient Conditions for Successful refactoring	Indicators of Success full Refactoring				
	Enhanced Readability	Enhanced Performance	Enhanced Maintainability	Extensibility	Reduced Technical Debt
Clean Code	Direct	Direct	Direct	Direct	Direct
Understand Software Design	Direct	Direct	Indirect	Direct	Direct
Testing	Indirect	Direct	Indirect	Indirect	Direct
Clear Objective	Direct	Direct	Direct	Direct	Direct
Follow Coding standards	Direct	Direct	Direct	Indirect	Direct
Incremental steps	Direct	Direct	Direct	Indirect	Direct
Use of DevOps	Direct	Direct	Direct	Direct	Direct

The comparative analysis shows that clean code and DevOps plays an important role in successful refactoring by having direct impact over all the benefits of successful refactoring.

Various types of benefits that developers get from successful refactoring shown in Figure 2.1.

FIGURE 2.1 Various Types of Refactoring Benefits (Kim *et al.*, 2014)

In FIGURE 2.1 the statistical data provides the base to validate our work and gives statistical data for the result of research.

CHAPTER 3

CONCLUSION

This research essay presents all the sufficient conditions for successful refactoring and comparative analysis of the conditions over successfulness of refactoring

3.1 Summary

Refactoring is changing the structure of code without any change in its external behavior. For successful refactoring, sufficient conditions include clean code that is more maintainable and readable code, code standards, use of DevOps, understanding of System design, running all test cases successfully etc. After detailed literature review the comparative analysis of these conditions depicts that, the impact of conditions over successfulness of refactoring is important to understand. It minimizes the time and effort for software product development. The research essay, presented a comparative analysis for conditions having direct and indirect impact over the benefits of refactoring. To validate the work statistical data collection performed to see the impact of conditions for successful refactoring. The results of research show that considering all conditions are important for successful refactoring but clean code and DevOps are the most important conditions for the successful refactoring.

3.2 Research Essay Contributions

There are two contributions, which are as follows. First contribution is exploring all the sufficient conditions for successful refactoring by detailed literature of review. Second contribution is comparative analysis and impact over the benefits of successful refactoring.

6.3 Conclusion and Future Work

After successful completion of exploring the sufficient conditions for successful refactoring, we plan to combine our proposed analysis with different techniques of refactoring. From the comparison results, it is concluded that our approach is easy to understand and value for the software engineers to consider the conditions for successful refactoring.

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